

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Nkrumah****FIRST NAME: Bernard****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. There are three key merits associated with the use of the WHO house style in writing. Which of the following is not one of the three? Choose the correct answer.**
 - House style ensures consistency by allowing readers to focus on the content of the material with greater ease and speed.
 - House style creates a level of uniformity to the corporate image of “one WHO.”
 - House style streamlines and increases the efficiency of the writing and editing process.
 - The house style is easier to understand and use by all.¹**
- 2. Following the WHO approved guidelines will help to ensure that language used in the WHO house style writing is free from bias and will avoid causing offence? Which of these is not consistent with the**

¹ WHO, *WHO Style Guide* (Malta: WHO, 2004), 1.

language, ethnicity and disability of this writing style. Choose the correct answer.

- It is not significant to acknowledge the diversity within racial and ethnic groups.²**
- A persons racial or cultural background should not be referred to unless there is a valid reason for doing so.
- Racial and cultural stereotypes are offensive and should be avoided at all times.
- Depersonalizing of persons with disabilities must be avoided at all times.

3. Which one of the following is not correct about presentation of research findings? Choose the correct answer.

- It must be logically and clearly derived from the findings.
- It must be content and context-specific.
- It must be capital and labor intensive.³**
- It must be practical and implementable.

4. Researchers are encouraged to seek answers by way of structuring the discussion according to all the interrelated activities except one? Choose the correct answer.

- By seeking significant patterns among the findings.
- Providing some sort of synthesis or integration.

² WHO, 57.

³ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Thousand Oaks, California: SAGE Publications, Inc., 2008), 158–60.

- Re-read and examine data, code data, place coded data in categories.**⁴
- Making use of description and interpretation.
5. **Information and sources required in citations must be able to answer these key questions except? Choose the correct answer.**
- Who wrote, edited, or translated the text.
- How many copies have been sold in the library or bookstore.**⁵
- Who published the work and when.
- What data identify the source: titles and subtitles of work or journal, volume number and edition.
6. **As researchers, it is very vital to cite all the sources of words, ideas and facts used in our work or papers. Which of the following best describes a benefit of citing sources? Choose the correct answer.**
- It helps readers to understand the work in connection with other works in the field of research.**⁶
- It helps to bring more recognition to the authors whose work has been cited.
- It is a way of making a paper or research more relevant
- It boosts the chances of the paper been published in a peer reviewed journal

⁴ Bloomberg and Volpe, 129.

⁵ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Eighth edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 87.

⁶ Turabian, 86.

7. **What are the three types of research questions used by researchers? Choose the correct answer.**

- Qualitative, Quantitative and Analytical.
- Applied, Quantitative and Analytical.
- Conceptual, Practical and Applied.**⁷
- Conceptual, Quantitative and Practical.

8. **Ways in which research findings can be shared with the scientific world could include all the following except? Choose the correct answer.**

- House to house dissemination.**⁸
- Oral presentations.
- Poster presentations.
- Journal Publications.

9. **Simple rules of thumb for writing effective papers could include all the following except? Choose the correct answer.**

- Do not make the writing boring and clumsy.
- Take the views you are discussing seriously.
- State the main thesis of your paper and stay focused.
- It is okay to lead with (or conclude with, or otherwise include) sweeping generalities.**⁹

⁷ Turabian, 16–17.

⁸ Turabian, 81–83.

⁹ EUCLID, *ACA-401 Coursepack* (Washington DC: Euclid University, 2015), 43–45.

10. **Euclid University requires students to use two different writing styles throughout the study program. Which of the following statements is true about these styles? Choose the correct answer.**

- Chicago Manual of Style is also called the APA Style.
- For the EUCLID program, the Turabian style is recommended for major papers.¹⁰**
- The Chicago and Turabian styles are not the same.
- Chicago style is mostly preferred for research papers, theses, and dissertations.

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¹⁰ EUCLID, 66.